

PERSPECTIVES AND STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING CONTINUING EDUCATION PROGRAMS IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD

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Abstract

The article aims, in principle, at presenting a glimpse of continuing education programs in the educational field, through an approach that combines theoretical analysis with data obtained by leading a micro-research on the perception of students in the field of Educational Sciences, master's level, from the University of Craiova, on these programs.

The first part of the article outlines the general theoretical framework of continuing education programs and highlights their significant role in responding to both the development needs of teachers and the requirements imposed by the constantly dynamic labor market. Additionally, the study identifies several

strategies for developing programs, both by referring to the specialized literature and by analyzing the investigative approach.

The second part of the article is dedicated to the investigative approach that tests the perception and expectations of the subjects regarding the way in which continuing education programs are conducted by applying a questionnaire with four closed questions.

The premises of the investigation were determined, firstly, by the diversity of teachers' opinions, and secondly by the importance of these programs in the current educational context dominated by current legislative changes and amendments.

Keywords: continuing education programs, educational field, development strategies

1. Theoretical framework and research premises

In recent years, continuous professional development has been a fundamental priority, being mentioned as an obligation in educational legislation or other regulations, and in some countries this obligation has been established in individual employment contracts of teachers or in collective agreements. (Albulescu & Catalano, coord., 2019, pp. 79-80)

Strategies for the development of continuous training programs have been a primary objective for continuous training providers and teaching staff in an educational context dominated by legislative, technological and, last but not least, socio-cultural changes. One of the most important strategies for the development of continuous training programs, adapted to current educational realities, refers to the shaping of a flexible and predictable curriculum. A flexible curriculum refers to the degree of its adaptation to changing educational contexts or to the continuously dynamic needs of learners. (OECD, 2024 apud. Albulescu, 2025, p. 113)

The curriculum constitutes, first of all, the core for the development strategies of continuing education programs in the educational field, and, secondly, it constitutes an indispensable element of the architecture of continuing education programs.

The national specialized literature offers a comprehensive picture of the conceptualization of the notion, and the most accessible is that according to which the curriculum of continuing education programs for teachers represents "the training offer of a provider, the system of educational processes and direct and indirect learning and training experiences offered to trainees and experienced by them in educational contexts that provide opportunities for training." (Șerbănescu & Bocoș & Ioja, 2020, p.173)

A comprehensive definition of curriculum is that given by Hass and Parkay, and according to them the curriculum is the sum of all experiences,,that learners have within a learning program whose purpose is to fulfill broad goals and corresponding specific objectives, which is planned in terms of a theoretical and practical framework or of an educational practice, present or grounded in the past.”(Hass & Parkay, 1993, apud. Strungă, 2020, p. 17)

The intercultural curriculum has aroused increased interest for practitioners and researchers in the field of education, and in the vision of Professor Bunăiașu, the concept refers to,,all educational processes and intercultural learning experiences, in formal, non-formal and informal contexts, throughout lifelong education.”(Bunăiașu, 2015, p. 45)

In the current educational context, dominated by artificial intelligence, the development of digital skills is one of the essential priorities for both teachers and learners.

Digital skills cannot be viewed separately from the curriculum, their integration into the curriculum constituting for educational institutions the

premise that young people will have an increased chance of professional success after graduation. (Albulescu, 2025, p. 136)

Autonomous learning is one of the postmodern training strategies in which the process of knowledge and development of skills depends largely on the learners, in opposition to the traditional approach, in which the teacher is the central element and makes the most important decisions. (Ibidem, p.155)

The need for an investigative approach is absolutely necessary to identify coherent and current strategies for developing continuing education programs in the educational field.

The basic hypothesis of the research starts from the situation in which, if continuing education programs have content focused on digital tools, as well as on postmodern and diversified training strategies, then a conducive framework is created for the professional development of teachers in the educational field.

2. Research objectives

The objectives of the investigative approach are the following:

1. Verifying the opinions of the subjects regarding the prospects for the development of continuing education programs in the educational field.
2. Identifying coherent and current strategies for optimizing continuing education programs in the educational field.
3. Identifying and including current thematic areas within continuing education programs in the educational field.
4. Developing certain skills in relation to European requirements within continuing education programs.

3. Research Methodology and Results

The group of subjects consisted of 63 students in the field of Educational Sciences, master's level, from the University of Craiova, educational program

which is generally attended by teachers that unfold their activity in educational field.

The research instrument used was the questionnaire, applied to the subjects to investigate opinions regarding the premises and strategies for developing continuing education programs in the educational field.

Next, five items with predetermined answers, included in the Google Forms form applied to the group of subjects, are subjected to analysis.

1. Do you consider that current in-service training programs meet the real needs of teachers?

63 responses

2. Participation in continuing education courses is, according to the legislation in force, once every 2 years. Do you think these courses should be organized more often?

63 responses

3. To what extent do you believe that the integration of artificial intelligence-based tools could contribute to improving in-service training programs for teachers?

63 responses

4. Which of the following thematic areas included in the continuing education program are of particular interest to you?

63 responses

- Digital accounts 47(74.6%)

- Equal opportunities and gender equality

- Education for the environment

- Intercultural education

5. How do you prefer continuing education programs for teachers to be conducted?

63 responses

The results of the questionnaire show that the way of carrying out interactions within continuing education programs held at least every two years, that take place in online format, through e-learning platforms, is mostly embraced, while traditional face-to-face interactions play a significantly smaller role.

With the identification of strategies for the development of continuing education programs in the educational field, we witness the shaping of the program's goals consisting in the professional development of trainees by relating to individual training needs, educational changes and educational policies.

The field of digital skills comes to predominate in continuing education programs, while other important areas such as environmental education, equal opportunities, gender and intercultural education are relegated to the background, an aspect also highlighted by the analysis of the answers provided by respondents to the item included in the questionnaire, this because in today's society, digital technologies create a new framework for relating to knowledge, communication and culture. (Albulescu, 2025, p. 138)

The optimization of continuing education programs in the educational field is achieved according to the latest trends by integrating digital tools.

Through digital tools, both trainees and trainers as an integral part of these continuing education programs have access to teaching materials beyond

traditional textbooks, to scientific articles in electronic format, to open educational resources, to online platforms or to numerous study applications. (ibidem, p. 149)

4. Conclusions

Continuing training programs are of particular importance in the current educational context, which necessitated their regulation in the new education law. More specifically, the pre-university education law no. 198/2023 contains express provisions, stating that "teaching staff in pre-university education are obliged to participate at least once every 2 years in at least one accredited continuing training program, according to a plan established at the level of the educational unit, based on the training needs analysis developed by the CNFDCCD" (art. 188 paragraph 7 of Law no. 198/2023).

Given that participation in continuing training courses is not only a right, but also an obligation provided for by the legislation in force, we considered it necessary that one of the items be built around this legal requirement, according to which continuing training must be carried out once every two years. The analysis of the responses revealed that more than half of the respondents consider the time interval provided for by the law sufficient.

As our country's legislation must be harmonized with European Union legislation, we consider it appropriate to create a unified European curricular framework regarding continuing education programs in the educational field in order to facilitate easier professional mobility.

In conclusion, in line with the dynamics of social relations and the ever-changing demands of the labor market, the development of continuing education programs in the educational field generally focuses on the integration of digital tools, as well as online interaction to the detriment of face-to-face interaction in

order to facilitate access to training and to remove any time and place barriers that may arise.

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